

many plants in several crosses was delayed despite the short-day treatment. Some plants in crosses such as G. Benton 1101/IR42, DA29/IR42, and BR4/Patnai 23 matured as late as 134 days after sowing.

A study of the parents showed that crosses involving two parents of long basic vegetative phase (BVP) (such as G. Benton 1101/IR42 and DA29/IR42) resulted in delayed flowering of many lines (see table). But in crosses where one or both parents have short BVP, such as Silewah/Hokkai 241, the resulting progeny are early flowering.

The delay in flowering of certain crosses is mostly the result of long BVP. Thus, a line with a BVP of 60 days will take longer than 100 days to mature. Such crosses tend to diminish the advantage of RGA because the possibility of 3 generations/year becomes difficult.

The BVP, if known, should be consi-

Basic vegetative phase (BVP) and growth duration of varieties involved in crosses. IRRI, 1981.

	BVP	Growth duration (days)
G. Benton 1101	60	F ₂ = 122
IR42	49	F ₃ = 99
DA29	41	F ₂ = 113
IR42	49	F ₃ = 134
BR4	40	F ₂ = 115
Patnai 23	41	F ₃ = 106
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 82
Hokkai 241	13	F ₃ = 67
		F ₄ = 70
		F ₅ = 75
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 85
IR2793-80-1/ IR747B2-6-3	short	
Silewah	45	F ₂ = 103
IR52	medium	

dered in determining what crosses to run through RGA. Crosses with long BVP that are insensitive to photoperiod could be planted in the field because the growth duration in the RGA is not considerably shortened and, in some cases, is actually delayed. ■

Performance of IR36 in Karnataka, India

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In Karnataka, about 55% of the rice area is planted to 16 recommended high yielding varieties. Some more area could be brought under high yielding rices by filling the extension gap. But special varieties with multiple resistance, interme-

diate plant stature, and earliness are needed for the area still planted to native rices.

Recent research and minikit results have indicated that IR36 has potential to supplement the currently recommended early-maturing, high-yielding varieties. IR36 has four attractive features: long slender grain, tolerance for salinity, tolerance for iron deficiency, and early maturity. This combination of characteristics cannot be found in any variety on the current recommended list.

Performance of IR36 in Karnataka, South India, 1978-80.

Year	Season	Variety ^a	Sites ^b (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over check varieties
1978	Wet	IR36	5	5.1	
		Rasi		4.7	9
		IR20		4.6	11
		Ratna		4.2	21
1978	Upland trial	IR36	1	4.8	
		Rasi		4.4	9
1979	Wet	IR36	3	4.4	—
		Mandya Vani		3.9	13
		IR20		4.4	—
		Pushpa		4.0	10
1980	Wet	IR36	1	4.1	
		Madhu		3.8	8
		Pushpa		3.3	24

^aSome check varieties were not included at all sites. ^bMandya, Mangalore, Mugad, Dhadesugur, Hebbal, Nagenahalli, and Ankoal, Karnataka, India.

Performance tests conducted at different sites and across seasons in the rice experiment stations of Karnataka show the superiority of IR36 over Rasi, Ratna, Mandya Vani, Madhu, IR20, and Pushpa (see table).

IR36 was also evaluated for two seasons through minikit trials in farmers' fields and will be tested for a third season. It is hoped that IR36 will supplement other early varieties in the districts of Bangalore, Tumkur, Kolar, Chitradurga, Bellary, Raichur, Shimoga, and Dharwad. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Grain quality

Aflatoxins in Sri Lankan rice

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Carcinogenic aflatoxins are produced by the fungi *Aspergillus flavus* and *A. parasiticus* that commonly grow on cereals and legumes in tropical climates. In Sri Lanka, rice is mainly consumed as raw *kekulu* processed (with or without bran) or parboiled rice (brown or polished). In parboiling, rough rice is soaked, steamed and sun-dried before milling. The chances of grains becoming moldy during this procedure are high. Various types of rice were examined for the relationship of processing method to aflatoxin contamination.

About 27% of the rough rice samples collected from Kandy were contami-

Occurrence of aflatoxin B₁ in Sri Lankan rice.

Rice	B ₁ (ppm)	Rice class
BG90-2	0	rough
BG94-1	0	rough
BG400-1	trace +	rough
BG379-2	0	rough
BG34-8	0.056	rough
MI39-193-1	0	rough
MI639-124-23	0	rough
MI290-32	0	rough
BW265	0.024	rough
BW272-6B	0	rough
BW272-8	0	rough
Parboiled samba	0	polished
Parboiled	0.128	polished
Parboiled	0.234	brown rice

nated with aflatoxin B₁ (see table). The level (0.234 ppm) detected in parboiled (brown) rice collected from Peradeniya was much higher than the tolerable level (0.01 ppm) in developed countries. The natural contamination of rough rice

BG34-8 and BW265 could indicate a higher susceptibility of new improved varieties to toxigenic strains of *Aspergillus*.

Twelve rice varieties tested for susceptibility at moisture content 30% were

artificially inoculated with two toxigenic strains of *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus*. All 12 were susceptible. They also produced very high levels of toxins (above 0.300 ppm) in 2 weeks of incubation at 25°C. ■

GENETICE EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Leaf scald disease of rice in Andhra Pradesh

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During a disease monitoring tour to RRRS, Nellore, in February 1981, leaf scald disease caused by *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka and Yokogi was observed in many rice varieties on the farm. Disease-affected specimens were collected, the causal organism was isolated, and its pathogenicity was confirmed at AICRIP, Hyderabad. On the

basis of all morphological characters, the fungus is identical to what Ou described in 1972.

The conidial suspension of the fungus was prepared from 7-day-old streaked culture on potato dextrose agar in petri dishes. Two susceptible varieties — TN1 and EUP-1582 — (known from the earlier work with the Ponnampet isolate of the pathogen) were grown in pots. When the plants were at panicle initiation stage, they were inoculated with the clip inoculation method and then kept in humid chambers for 72 hours. Five days after inoculation, 2- to 3-mm-long water-soaked lesions at the clipped ends of leaves were observed. The lesions gradually moved downwards and within

12 days covered 12-15 cm of the leaf blade, turning straw color with transverse banding. From the fresh advancing lesions, the fungus was reisolated and identified as *R. oryzae*. This is the first record of leaf scald occurrence in Andhra Pradesh.

Various experimental trials have shown the following varieties or cultures as susceptible to leaf scald disease at Nellore: NLR 11214, NLR 10859, NLR 18235, NLR 18161, NLR 17906, NLR 17039, NLR 16696, NLR-T 197, RNR 89128, RNR 36178, RNR 87877, K H 998, Rajendra, KLN H 361-1-1-6-2, KLN H 36, MTU 6099, MTU 5249, MTU 5283, MTU 5410-9, CR 181-62-15, CR 42-10-231, RP 1033-43-2, PS 1-44-624, IR20, IR34, BPT 1235, IET 6844, IET 7532, IET 6069, IET 6097, IET 6560, IET 7041, IET 6661, IET 6896, IET 7237, and IET 7042. ■

Disease reaction of advanced rice cultures

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In Kuttanad, the rice bowl of Kerala, 100% coverage of high yielding rice varieties has been achieved. Severe incidences of sheath blight disease caused by *Rhizoctonia solani*, sheath rot disease caused by *Acrocyndrium oryzae*, and bacterial blight caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* occur in the area. To develop varieties that can tolerate those diseases, rice cultures developed at the RRS, Moncompu, were evaluated.

The cultures were screened repeatedly for 2 years in the field and in the greenhouse, and artificial inoculations by standard techniques were done. Disease intensity was scored by the IRRS Standard Evaluation System for Rice scales, 2 weeks before harvest. The mean disease

Disease reactions^a of advanced rice cultures. Rice Research Station, Moncompu, Kerala, India.

Culture of Variety	Mean sheath blight score	Mean sheath rot score	Mean bacterial blight score
M11-57-5-1 ^b	1.25	2.20	0.35
M1544-2	2.62	3.67	2.75
M15-36-2 ^c	0.00	2.95	5.15
M1537-2	2.00	1.85	2.10
M23-100-2-2	1.36	1.20	1.15
M23-16-1-1	1.35	1.05	1.35
M23-17-1-1	0.25	0.85	1.37
M23-69-1-1	0.60	0.45	1.35
M23-69-1-1-1	3.95	1.75	0.65
M23-74-1-2-1	2.07	2.57	1.97
M23-17-1-3	4.12	2.50	2.47
M23-69-1-2	2.35	2.42	1.80
M23-83-1-1	1.37	2.80	0.35
M22-65-2-4	2.02	4.25	1.62
M22-184-1-1	1.50	3.92	2.50
M14-59-2	1.42	3.35	2.47
M23-74-1-1	0.70	2.22	1.62
M24-211-1	0.67	3.17	1.85
M1537-1	1.15	3.00	1.45
M22-67-3-2	1.62	2.70	2.40
Jyothi (susceptible check)	4.12	2.70	4.52
TN1 (" ")	2.67	3.32	4.21

^aScored by the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice scales of 0-9. ^bReleased as Bhadra during 1978. ^cReleased as MO 5 during 1980.

scores recorded for each entry are in the table.

M15-36-2 (MO 5), M23-17-1-1, M23-

69-1-1, M23-74-1-1, and M24-211-1 showed good tolerance for sheath blight (score < 1); M23-17-1-1 and M23-69-1-1